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CONCEPTUALIZING AND MODELLING THE GAME-BASED EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT FOR FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

ASSILOVA SABINA ORALKHANOVNA

Academy “Bolashaq”, master degree student, Karaganda city, Republic of Kazakhstan

Scientific supervisor: GAZIKHANOVA ZHANAR GAZIZOVNA

Academy “Bolashaq”, associate professor, PhD, Karaganda city, Republic of Kazakhstan

Abstract: *The increasing difficulty of maintaining students' motivation in foreign language classrooms requires the search for new approaches and models to the organization of the teaching-and-learning process and more effective teaching methods. This article presents the conceptual study of the game-based educational environment (GBEE) in teaching foreign languages that integrates game mechanics, digital technologies, and communicative methodologies. The study proposes a model of GBEE outlining its key components, principles and pedagogical implications. The article contributes to deepening the theoretical understanding of the GBEE and argues that the GBEE represents an evolution from isolated gamified techniques toward a holistic, dynamic learning ecosystem that fosters motivation, autonomy, and communicative competence in language learners.*

Key words: *game-based, educational environment, gamification, language acquisition, communicative approach, constructivist learning, interactive learning, engagement, motivation, digital tools.*

Аннотация: *Возрастающая сложность поддержания мотивации учащихся на уроках иностранного языка требует поиска новых подходов и моделей организации учебного процесса, а также более эффективных методов обучения. В данной статье представлено концептуальное исследование игровой образовательной среды (GBEE) в обучении иностранным языкам, которая объединяет игровую механику, цифровые технологии и коммуникативные методики. В исследовании предлагается модель GBEE, описывающая ее ключевые компоненты, принципы и педагогические аспекты. Статья способствует углублению теоретического понимания GBEE и утверждает, что GBEE представляет собой эволюцию от использования изолированных игровых методов к целостной, динамичной экосистеме обучения, способствующей развитию мотивации, автономии и коммуникативной компетентности учащихся.*

Ключевые слова: *игровой, образовательная среда, геймификация, овладение языком, коммуникативный подход, конструктивистское обучение, интерактивное обучение, вовлечённость, мотивация, цифровые инструменты.*

Introduction

In contemporary education, where digital interaction and entertainment occupy a significant part of learners' daily lives, maintaining motivation in foreign language classrooms has become increasingly challenging. As a result, educators are forced to seek more innovative and engaging environments to enhance the learning process.

Games are one of the most widely recognized and extensively used teaching methods in education. Numerous studies on the use of game-based methods, tools, and formats in language teaching have demonstrated their effectiveness across a range of language proficiency levels and age groups. While the benefits of game-based learning are evident for younger learners, researches also highlight its applicability to adult learners, despite initial perceptions that such an approach may be inadequate and unnecessary in higher education settings. Although previous studies have explored the role of game elements in language learning, there is still a lack of comprehensive research on the fully integrated game-based educational environments (GBEE). Therefore, this article aims to

conceptualize and model the GBEE in foreign language instruction by analyzing literature, identifying its key components, and synthesizing theoretical perspectives. Following the stated aim, the research questions can be formulated as follows: How can a game-based educational environment be conceptualized? What are the key components and characteristics of such an environment? How can the GBEE be created in foreign language classrooms?

Defining the game-based educational environment (GBEE)

This study follows a qualitative design based on literature analysis and lesson modeling. The methodology involves an in-depth analysis of literature, focusing on peer-reviewed articles published between 2020 and 2024. Sources were selected based on their relevance to define and conceptualize a game educational environment. Additionally, this study used a comparative analysis of definitions and game-based educational models and aims to synthesize various theoretical frameworks on gamification and language acquisition to develop a comprehensive understanding of how gamified environments function within educational settings. Based on key findings from the literature we designed a lesson plan to illustrate the practical application of game-based educational environment.

A systematic review of scholarly sources from 2020-2024 was conducted to identify key trends and developments in gamification for language learning. Based on the synthesis of previous studies, this paper proposes a structured definition of a game educational environment. Key characteristics such as interactivity, challenge-based learning, and student autonomy are explored through theoretical models.

While this study provides a conceptual foundation for game-based learning, future empirical research is needed to validate these theoretical findings in real-world classroom settings. Potential challenges, such as technological constraints and varying student engagement levels, are discussed.

Gamification in education has been widely studied, with researchers emphasizing its potential to enhance engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes. We have divided all reviewed sources into several groups. First group is “role of motivation”, to which we attributed the following study.

One of the main problems in teaching English today, which teachers are trying to deal with, is low motivation and strong resistance to learning a foreign language. As Silalahi (2019) notes in her article, “...because of the broad and complex scope of English, not a few people find it difficult to understand English. This is also experienced by most students in schools. They tend to dislike learning English because it is difficult to understand” [1].

The second group includes studies related to “digital game-based learning”. It is worth mentioning that most of the works that have analyzed, compared and examined the use of games in language teaching at school, the use of real computer digital games in language teaching and language skills development was investigated, for example, as in the work of Hanghøj, Kabel, and Hannibal Jensen in which they conducted an extensive and significant comparative analysis of existing researches in the field of the use of digital games and their impact on the development of literacy and the study of native and foreign languages [2]. Nevertheless, they do not extensively explore the role of gamification in structuring these environments. This study mostly builds on existing research by proposing an integrated approach that leverages both digital and interactive game elements. In the following studies Yahoui, Yolageldili and Arikan carried out a large work on the practical evaluation of the effectiveness of using various educational games in teaching grammar and improving the vocabulary of schoolchildren [3, 4].

In the existing works we reviewed, the authors simply studied the inclusion of games in the educational process as an additional means of motivation and, accordingly, increasing the effectiveness of language learning and the development of a particular skill, depending on the purpose of each author. In this case, we are leading to the fact that very few studies have been conducted in order to create a game-based educational environment, that is, not a virtual English language learning classroom completely designed as a game/quest. We have identified only a couple of studies with a similar purpose, which form the third group “game educational design”, the first work by Brooke in which she examines “the effect of game design on foreign language acquisition through a French language game design project” [5]; the second work is “experiences with the design of game-like

applications in 3-D virtual environments as well as its impact on student motivation and learning” [6]. However, these studies primarily assess isolated game elements rather than comprehensive game-based environments.

Previous studies have often considered gamification as an auxiliary motivational tool rather than a comprehensive educational model. Gamification usually involves simply adding game elements to traditional learning without fundamentally restructuring the learning process; learning is not modeled on the principle of a game, but only receives some of its elements. It is used to increase student engagement, but does not change the logic of the educational process itself. While, in contrast to conventional learning, where a game can only be an auxiliary tool, in a game-based educational environment the learning process is modeled by analogy with real game mechanics, including the presence of game characters (avatars, roles), levels - interactive tasks based on a challenge (challenge-based learning), that is, completing tasks is perceived as overcoming levels in a game, points, ratings, and achievement tables are introduced. Thus, the main difference lies in the degree of game integration: in a game-based educational environment, a game is the learning environment itself, and in gamification it is only an auxiliary element of motivation.

From our point of view, one of the main reasons for this approach is the emphasis on motivation instead of methodology. Many gamification studies focus on increasing motivation, as has been emphasized earlier, rather than on analyzing deep changes in the learning process. This is justified by the fact that it is much easier to study engagement indicators (for example, frequency of participation, number of completed tasks) compared to qualitative changes in mastering the material. In addition, one can note the commercial focus, for example, educational platforms and courses more often use gamification to increase student retention, rather than to change teaching methods. An important reason is the lack of connection with educational theories, that is, gamification is often considered in isolation from methodological foundations, such as a communicative approach or constructivist learning. As a result, game mechanics are added, but not adapted to educational goals. Gamification studies rarely take into account the context of learning a foreign language, and are more often used for entertainment. Thus, the gap is explained by the fact that gamification is viewed narrowly – as a way to increase motivation, and not as a tool for designing the educational process.

Therefore, in this article we will consider and formulate a definition of the concept of a game educational environment, based on the analysis of literary sources and supplement it with methodological visual material in the form of a lesson plan. Finally, the last but not least group of studies is “theoretical perspectives on educational environments”. There are quite a lot of points of view, definitions, characteristics and components of the educational environment. For example, Dergacheva E.V. understands the educational environment as “a natural or artificially created socio-cultural environment of a student, including various types of means and content of education that can ensure the productive activity of the student” [7]. The definition is quite broad and general, but quite practical, in our opinion, the author just notes one of the main characteristics, the essence of the environment itself - the socio-cultural environment of the student, and it is noted that it can be natural or artificially created, that is, different formats of training are immediately taken into account. It is also important to focus on the productive activity of the student, because it implies that the environment is not just created and exists, but affects the student and his development. However, this definition does not include a component of feedback.

In turn, Tarasov S.V. provides the following more comprehensive definition: “the educational environment can be characterized as a set of social, cultural, and also specially organized psychological and pedagogical conditions in an educational institution, as a result of which interaction with an individual personality formation occurs” [8]. In this case, not only the conditions created at school are taken into account, but also the fundamental psychological and pedagogical aspect, and the equally important interaction of the individual with the environment. That is, the environment is considered not just as a background, but as a living system.

Many psychologists and educators consider the educational environment from the point of view of synergetics, emphasizing that, in essence, the educational environment is a systemically formed

space in which the interaction of subjects of the educational process with the external environment is realized, as a result of which the individual personality traits of the student are revealed. Baeva I.A. derived the following concept: “the educational environment is a psychological and pedagogical reality containing specially organized conditions for the formation of personality, as well as opportunities for development included in the social and spatial-subject environment, while its psychological essence is a set of activity-communicative acts and relationships of participants in the educational process” [9]. In our opinion, one of the most complete and capacious definitions, the main distinguishing feature seems to be taking into account the social and spatial-subject environment, thus the environment is not only a teacher and a student, but also an atmosphere, that is, the very idea of the educational environment is emphasized.

Finally, in his work “Educational environment: from modeling to design”, Yasvin V.A. interprets it as follows: “... by the educational environment we will understand the system of influences and conditions for the formation of personality according to a given pattern, as well as opportunities for its development contained in the social and spatial-subject environment” [10]. The approach stands out for its consistency, it takes into account both space and social conditions, and pedagogical impact/influence.

As for the main game component, which is the essence of our idea, there was only one definition for this concept by Grinyavichene N.-E.T. “The subject-game environment is a specially organized space that includes a set of specially selected objects, toys, play equipment, furniture, etc. for the implementation of specific types of children's activities” [11]. This definition was singled out only because it focuses on the organization of space, since it is this that will mainly set the atmosphere of the game.

Now let us consider the concept of the educational environment in the learning and teaching of a foreign language. As noted by Galskova N.D. and Gez N.I. due to the peculiarities of the modern educational environment, “teaching foreign languages should be aimed at developing the autonomy of the student in the learning activity of mastering a specific language being studied” [12], a distinctive feature is the allocation of the student’s autonomy, today it is especially important that the student does not just listen and mechanically memorize, but learns with parallel development of independent work skills.

Obdalova O.A. concludes “... the educational environment of the new type acts as a means and condition for communication-oriented teaching of a foreign language, which is based on a model of real communication and the latest means and methods of teaching. Considering that the process of real speech interaction always takes place in a certain situation when teaching a foreign language outside the natural linguistic and cultural environment, teachers are the designers of the information and educational learning environment and should try to model it taking into account the principle of authenticity” [13]. This definition shows that language teaching requires a communication-oriented approach and modeling of the environment as close as possible to real communication.

Thus, the educational environment is not static, but should be adapted to specific educational tasks and can be modeled, but it is important to take into account many factors and the necessary characteristics inherent in it. After analyzing various points of view and visions of the educational environment, its components and characteristics, not only in the general sense, but also in the context of learning a foreign language (in particular English) with our idea in a narrower gaming direction, we came to the following definition of a “game-based educational environment” – it is a dynamic and purposefully organized pedagogical space within the classroom, in which the educational process is based on game methods, techniques and elements, including specially selected and created didactic materials, interactive tasks, game technologies and digital/online tools aimed at developing cognitive, communicative and social skills of students with the active involvement of students through gaming activities.

Modeling the GBEE through a lesson plan

How can this be presented and implemented in a school lesson? For this purpose, we will demonstrate the functioning of a game educational environment using the example of a lesson plan for an English language lesson in the 7th grade and the corresponding applications/appendices.

Table 1. An example of a game-based lesson plan

Module	Holidays and Travel			
Teacher's name	Assilova S.O.			
Date	07.11.2025			
Grade: 7	Number of present:		Number of absent:	
Topic of the lesson	Holiday activities: Sports			
Learning objectives according to the curriculum	7.1.4.1 evaluate and respond constructively to feedback from other students; 7.1.6.1 organize and clearly present information in a form understandable to others; 7.1.7.1 develop and reinforce a consistent argument in oral and written speech; 7.1.9.1 use imagination to express your thoughts, ideas, experiences and feelings.			
Lesson objectives	Students will be able to engage in discussions about holidays and travel, demonstrating their understanding of new vocabulary through differentiated tasks that involve all types of speech activities (speaking, listening, writing, reading).			
Part of the lesson/ Time	Teacher's activity	Student's activity	Assessment	Resources

<p>Beginning of the lesson</p>	<p>Organization moment: 1. Greeting. The teacher greets the students and asks them to tune in to the lesson and remember their nicknames and characteristics of their characters (super strength) and get ready to complete the next level of their exciting game and get their points for it, the more points the higher the score and rating, and accordingly the place in the overall ranking among the classes!</p>	<p>Teachers greet them, remember their nicknames and characteristics, and tune in to the lesson.</p>		<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CQe4H8zFZfk&list=PL61EA7836AA4687F1&index=7</p>
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<p>Pre-learning</p>	<p>Warm-up activity: Guess the lesson topic. The teacher shows the board on the Miro platform on the monitor, the students click on the link and write their assumptions.</p>	<p>They reflect and express their assumptions Follow the link and write ideas on the stickers</p>	<p>For each more approximate answer, the student receives 5 points. The student gets 10 points for an accurate answer (at least half of the title).</p>	<p>https://mir.o.com/welcomeonboard/ZkxJajFmeUF4QlhWV2JGcTUxRVppbkw0NjFQZU9ONkdLcUpYcjNlc1lwQklzZkt4SWdpUDNwZmt6TVBlbmpLaUUrYittcGN6bEFUUm9XTE9aOXo0K3pqcTNUndCrbIR6U2VWeWdvSIFXM0szRVR6ZHk0bDZLVWh0WWhtT291bTkhZQ==?share_link_id=618350061888</p>
<p>Introduction</p>	<p>The teacher gives the students a link to the quizlet platform (or open it on the board) so that they can learn new words from different game modes. Then using the wheel of fortune, the teacher chooses a student, the student on whom the fortune falls must stand up and make a sentence with a new word.</p>	<p>Students learn new words in different modes, which is very convenient.</p>	<p>The student receives a token for correctly constructing a sentence using new words.</p>	<p>https://quizlet.com/kz/966899495/holidays-and-travel-flash-cards/?i=5xfhd1&x=1jqt (you can create module with any necessary list of words)</p>

<p>Group work</p>	<p>The teacher walks along the desks and the students pull out hats of different shapes and thus are then divided into groups (with identical hats). The teacher then plays the students a video (generated by AI) in which the director gives them a task. Gives a brochure to each team. We can also complete the assignment by providing worksheets that can be created using Canva and invite students not only to create an advertising statement, but also to make a brochure themselves (https://www.canva.com/design/DAGXImE_HqQ/vpIM5pRdfUiahIlbUU3E8g/edit?utm_content=DAGXImE_HqQ&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton; https://www.canva.com/design/DAGXIqEPJY8/YhhPBGXiaCRil-DFEewu0w/edit?utm_content=DAGXIqEPJY8&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton; https://www.canva.com/design/DAGXivu39J8/STJ5J1HKRwOVvUberKUtBA/edit?utm_content=DAGXivu39J8&utm_campaign=designshare&utm_medium=link2&utm_source=sharebutton)</p>	<p>Students are divided into groups, read a brochure, assign roles and prepare a presentation/performance</p>	<p>Criteria: - Fluency and pronunciation - Vocabulary and grammar - Creativity and engagement (team work – interaction, cooperation) - Task Completion</p>	<p>AI video: https://www.hedra.com/app/characters/1dc9a11b-536b-4ad0-9cc8-1ef800da501d/view Brochures https://s3-eu-west-1.amazonaws.com/images.cloudkuoni.co.uk/brochure/2020/discover_africa_2020.pdf (a lot of different brochure pages)</p>
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<p>End of the lesson Reflection</p>	<p>Shows students a QR code, which they use to get on the padlet board and give feedback. H/w: learn new words (quizlet)</p>	<p>Students follow the link and write comments answering feedback questions.</p>	
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Thus, we have shown one of the possible scenarios of a lesson built on the basis of game methods, using AI. Also in this example, you can notice the active use of smartphones by students, this decision on the part of the teacher in some lessons is explained by the fact that classes do not always have sufficient equipment (smart board or even a computer), so in this case we have developed a simple example of a lesson that can be implemented with or without all this in the classroom.

If we conduct a more detailed analysis of the lesson, then this lesson effectively integrates the game educational environment, actively involving students through a large number of interactive actions that gradually stimulate interest and motivation.

Gamification of the lesson, which is traced in such elements as nicknames, superpowers, a reward system (points, tokens), rating, the use of digital platforms (miro, quizlet, fortune wheel, hedra ai, padlet) makes learning competitive, which also plays a key role in the lesson and becomes one of the effective solutions to the problem that we have actualized above.

A well-structured role-playing task, where students take on different roles and participate in creating an advertising performance for a tour to different countries, including various activities, includes a socio-cultural component, cooperation and teamwork. In addition, the video created by AI adds an element of realism, making the task look like a real scenario, and not like a traditional group activity. The use of brochures adds an element of research, whereas the use of new words the context of real-life situations.

So how does the lesson illustrate the key characteristics of a game-based learning environment?

Interactivity and engagement (challenge-based learning) – pre-learning task; the use of game roles (nicknames, superpowers) – student’s autonomy; active participation in a group project (brochure and advertisement creation), the use/application of new vocabulary in a real context..

Digital tools – the introduction of a points and ratings system; using of digital platforms as Miro, Quizlet, Canva, Hedra AI, Padlet.

A game-based learning environment, according to the definition presented earlier, is a dynamic space where learning is based on game methods, tasks and technologies. This lesson demonstrates the advantages of this approach by creating a motivational environment - students are involved through a reward system (points, rating), developing cognitive skills - it is necessary not only to memorize vocabulary, but also to use it in a creative task, stimulating autonomous learning - students work in groups, create material themselves, solve communicative tasks, modeling real communication situations - tasks (creating a brochure, discussing tourist offers) are close to real scenarios. Thus, the lesson becomes an example of the comprehensive implementation of a game-based learning environment, and not just the use of individual game elements. As for the methodology, the game-based learning environment is effective precisely in the context of learning a foreign language, because it supports key language methods:

Communicative method can be seen in the fact that the lesson is built around real communicative tasks, also students work in pairs and groups, interact, and use language in situations – immersion learning. The entire lesson takes place in a game environment, where the language is used naturally, rather than in the traditional exercise format.

Constructivist approach is reflected in the fact that students construct knowledge themselves, working with authentic materials (tourist brochures, videos), the use of challenge-based learning (creation of an advertising project).

Conclusion

Earlier in the article, it was noted that most studies are limited to analyzing individual game elements, rather than a holistic game educational environment. However, this lesson includes a multi-platform approach (Miro, Quizlet, Padlet, AI video). Integrates role-playing learning and situational tasks, rather than just gamification. Corresponds to modern theories of language learning (communicative method, constructivism). Thus, this lesson can be used as an example of a fully structured game-based educational environment, and not just as a partial gamification of the learning process.

In this way, the teacher can create an interesting game educational environment that actively involves students. Analyzing the game-based learning environment in action, it can be concluded that it encompasses physical, social, emotional aspects that profoundly influence language acquisition and mastery as it provides great opportunities for interaction, exposure, and engagement with the target language.

Understanding the impact of the learning environment on language acquisition has a huge impact and significance in facilitating effective language learning experiences. By considering all aspects, components, and characteristics of the learning environment, teachers can create enriched environments that facilitate and promote language acquisition.

Thus, an analysis of the existing literature shows that an educational environment based on games can significantly increase students' motivation and improve language acquisition. In our modern world, it is obvious that the integration of interactive game elements increases cognitive activity and develops communication skills, as a result of vocabulary replenishment and automation of speech structures.

Theoretical models based on gamification and its principles are widely applicable, assume and show in practice the possibility of adaptation in various educational contexts, these same contextual differences can affect the implementation.

This article provides a theoretical basis for understanding the game educational environment in the process of learning a foreign language. Summarizing existing researches, emphasizing the potential benefits of gamification, we also recognize the need for further empirical verification. The results obtained are a contribution to both theoretical discussions on gamification and practical strategies for foreign language teachers.

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